

STABILITY OF COBALTIC BIGUANIDE COMPLEXES

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The stability of cobaltic *tris*-biguanide and cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide complexes have been determined from a measurement of the equilibrium constants of their reaction with acids and the acid dissociation constants of the biguanides concerned, together with the determination of the concentration of the cobaltic ion in solution by E.M.F. measurement in a Beckmann p_H -meter, on the basis of Bjerrum's theory relating to the formation of co-ordinatively saturated complexes by successive stages. The theory has been amply supported by the results obtained.

The individual instability constants k_2 , k_3 and k_1 for successive stages, as well as the overall constant K , for biguanide cobaltic complexes have been found to be much smaller than those of the cobaltic ammine complexes and the complexes of other metals, either of simple or inner metallic type. Biguanide cobaltic complexes are thus found to be the most stable of the cationic metal complexes, hitherto examined.

In spite of extensive researches for over half a century on co-ordination complexes, culminating recently in the application of the principles of quantum mechanics to account for their structure and behaviour, we are still not in a position to formulate a clear, definite and well-recognized principle guiding the formation of this highly interesting class of compounds. In recent years, however, much attention has been directed by several workers to a quantitative study of the mechanism of formation and stability of these complexes with a view to obtaining greater insight into their character. As a result thereof, much valuable information about them have already been collected with much more in prospect, which has made possible the occasional preparation of new types of complexes by defining precisely the conditions and range of their existence. Reference may in this connection be made to the comprehensive and pioneering work of Bjerrum ("Metalamine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Hasse and Son, Copenhagen, 1941), who has treated the problem on a statistical basis involving the formation of all intermediate stages in a reversible manner. Previous to this, Lamb and Larson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2024) studied the stabilities of a series of cobaltammines by determining the equilibrium constant for the reversible reaction

Bjerrum, however, emphasised the importance of the intermediate steps involved in the above overall reaction, viz.,

where M is the metal ion and A, the co-ordinating ligand. The equilibrium constants for the intermediate stages, termed formation constants or consecutive complexity constants by Bjerrum, were thus related to the overall equilibrium constant, or the complexity constant as termed by him. On the basis of Bjerrum's theory of reversible stepwise reactions Carlson, McReynolds and Verhoek (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1334) investigated the formation of the complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions with ethylenediamine and propylenediamine, and the complexes of Ag^+ ion with ethyl and diethylamine. The theory has also been applied to the stability of inner metallic complexes by Calvin and Wilson (*ibid.*, 1945, **47**, 2003) in order to make a quantitative survey regarding the influence of certain structural factors upon the stability of chelate complexes of bivalent copper bonded to four oxygen atoms. These copper complexes of *o*-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes and β -diketones are relatively insoluble in water, and hence the measurements had to be made in a water-dioxane (50/50) mixture. As a result of their study on twenty-one chelate compounds of bivalent copper, they attributed the changes in the complexity constant in relation to the structural change in the organic residue to two different force components responsible for binding the copper ion to the chelate residue. One of these was believed to be of the same character for both copper and hydrogen, and the other to be of a quite different nature derived from a resonance effect involving the copper atom.

Mellor and Maly (*Nature*, 1947, **159**, 370) following the work of Calvin and Wilson (*loc. cit.*) determined the values of formation and complexity constants of inner complexes formed by a series of bivalent metal ions (viz., of Pd, Cu, Ni, Pb, Co, Zn, Cd and Mg) with salicylaldehyde in dioxane-water (50/50) solution. The same authors (*Nature*, 1948, **161**, 436) compared the overall stability constants of the inner metallic complexes of salicylaldehyde-ethylenediamine (a quadridentate chelate molecule), which gave the following order for different metals: Pd, Cu, Ni, Co, Zn, Cd, Fe, Mn, Mg; the values decreasing from left to right. The two series thus show a closely similar order.

Ackermann, Prue and Schwarzenbach (*Nature*, 1949, **163**, 723) measured the stability constants of the complexes formed by different metal ions with $\beta\beta'\beta''$ -triamino-triethylamine, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3$, (tren), which behaves as a quadridentate molecule providing four points of attachment for the metal ion. The stability constants were evaluated from the acid dissociation constant of the amine and the equilibrium constant of the reaction

The stability constant values of different metal complexes generally followed the same order as that observed with ammonia or ethylenediamine. The copper complex was, however, found to be less stable than the corresponding ethylenediamine compound, due presumably to factors of steric nature, which renders almost impossible the assumption of a planar configuration.

Complex compounds of biguanide and substituted biguanide with metallic elements, which have formed a subject of investigation in this laboratory for several years, belong to the class of inner metallic complexes of the third order (cf. Rây and Dutt,

this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 563) and can give rise to many water-soluble salts. These, therefore, furnish suitable materials for a study of the mechanism of complex formation and the stability of the resulting complexes on the basis of Bjerrum's theory. Biguanide or biguanidinium ion behaves as a bifunctional group occupying two co-ordination positions, while a dibiguanide or its ion functions as a quadridentate group occupying four co-ordination positions. In the present paper we shall describe the results of our study on cobaltic *tris*-biguanide and cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanide complexes. The procedure adopted for the purpose, however, differs somewhat from those of the previous workers in view of the nature of the complexes concerned. The biguanide molecule itself possesses a tautomeric structure, each of which again may possess a resonating character :

The matter becomes further complicated in the case of a trivalent metal complex like that of cobalt.

The method adopted was as follows. The decomposition of the cobaltic *tris*-biguanide complex was studied in the presence of acid and the equilibrium constant of the reaction was determined. The overall reaction in the presence of acid can be given by :

where BigH_2^+ represents a biguanidinium ion.

The reaction in fact proceeds in three successive stages as shown below :

The successive equilibrium constants for reactions (2), (3) and (4) are denoted respectively by k'_1 , k'_2 and k'_3 . These are related to the overall equilibrium constant K' given by the reaction (1).

$$\begin{aligned} K' &= \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}] [\text{BigH}_2^+]^3}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{+++}] [\text{H}^+]^3} \\ &= \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}] [\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})^{+++}] [\text{H}^+]} \times \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})^{+++}] [\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{+++}] [\text{H}^+]} \\ &\quad \times \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{+++}] [\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{+++}] [\text{H}^+]} \\ &= k'_1 \cdot k'_2 \cdot k'_3 \quad \dots (5) \end{aligned}$$

The values of $[Co^{+++}]$, $[BigH_2^+]^2$, $[H^+]^2$ and $[Co(BigH)_3^{+++}]$ should therefore be known in order to obtain K' .

The concentration of Co^{+++} was determined from the well known Nernst equation

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{Co^{+++}}}{a_{Co^{++}}},$$

where E = observed E.M.F. corrected to normal hydrogen electrode; E_0 = standard electrode potential for cobaltic-cobaltous system; and $a_{Co^{+++}}$ and $a_{Co^{++}}$ are the activities of cobaltic and cobaltous ions in solution. The values of E_0 for cobaltic-cobaltous system is, as given by Lamb and Larson (*loc. cit.*), +1.817 volts at 25°, the temperature coefficient being +0.00169 volt.

The concentration of biguanidinium ion, $BigH_2^+$, was evaluated from the acid dissociation constant of biguanide hydrochloride as follows. In acid solution biguanide is present as biguanidinium ion. In low acid concentration a considerable amount of it is present as $BigH_2^+$ ion and to a negligible extent as $BigH_3^{++}$ ion. The reaction proceeds in two steps:

The acid dissociation constant k_1^* corresponding to (a) is given by

$$k_1^* = \frac{C_{BigH} \cdot C_{H^+}}{C_{BigH_2^+}} \quad \dots (6)$$

and that corresponding to (b) by

$$k_2^* = \frac{C_{BigH_2^+} \cdot C_{H^+}}{C_{BigH_3^{++}}} \quad \dots (7)$$

At low concentration of hydrogen ion, let C_A = the concentration of the acid added, C'_A (from a_{H^+}) = the concentration of the acid after reaction, C_B = the concentration of the total biguanide.

Then

$$C_A - C'_A = C_{BigH_2^+};$$

$$C_B = C_{BigH} + C_{BigH_2^+};$$

$$\text{Therefore, } C_{BigH} = C_B - C_A + C'_A$$

$$\text{Hence } k_1^* = \frac{(C_B - C_A - C'_A) \cdot [H^+]}{(C_A - C'_A)} \quad \dots (8)$$

At a higher concentration of hydrogen ion,

$$C_A - C'_A = 2C_{BigH_3^{++}} + C_{BigH_2^+};$$

$$C_B = C_{BigH_3^{++}} + C_{BigH_2^+};$$

Hence $C_{BigH_3^{++}} = C_A - C'_A - C_B$, and $C_{BigH_2^+} = 2C_B - C_A + C'_A$.

$$\text{Therefore, } k_2^* = \frac{(2C_B - C_A + C'_A)[H^+]}{(C_A - C'_A - C_B)} \quad \dots (9)$$

The acid dissociation constants, k_1^* and k_2^* of biguanide were thus determined.

The concentration of hydrogen ion H^+ or $[H^+]$ in (5) was deduced from the measured p_H of the acid solution of the complex.

The concentration of $Co(BigH)_3^{+++}$ was obtained by calculation as shown below.

From these the value of K' was obtained. The overall instability or dissociation constant K of the complex is given by:

Now let C denote the molar concentration of the complex taken and C_3, C_2, C_1 the respective concentrations of $Co(BigH)_3^{+++}, Co(BigH_2)^{++}$ and $Co(BigH)^{+}$, so that

$$C = C_3 + C_2 + C_1 \text{ (neglecting } Co^{+++}) \quad \dots (11)$$

If x be the total biguanide liberated from the complex then

$$3C - x = 3C_3 + 2C_2 + C_1 \quad \dots (12)$$

The acid consumed in the reaction was obtained from the concentration of the acid added and the final p_H values of the complex solutions; the latter was reduced to the acid concentration value from a graph relating the measured p_H with the negative logarithm of acid concentration (Randall and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 989). The difference between this and the concentration of the acid added gave the amount of the acid used up by the reaction with the complex. Let this be denoted by Z . Evidently,

$$Z = C_{BigH_2^+} + 2C_{BigH^{++}} = C_{BigH^+} \left(1 + \frac{2C_{BigH_2^{++}}}{C_{BigH^+}} \right)$$

$$= C_{BigH^+} \left(1 + \frac{2[H^+]}{k_2^*} \right) = C_{BigH^+} \left(\frac{k_2^* + 2[H^+]}{k_2^*} \right) \quad \dots (13)$$

Therefore,
$$C_{BigH_2^+} = \frac{k_2^* Z}{k_2^* + 2[H^+]} \quad \dots (14)$$

Total biguanide liberated from the complex,

$$x = C_{BigH_2^+} + C_{BigH^{++}} = C_{BigH^+} \left(1 + \frac{C_{BigH_2^{++}}}{C_{BigH^+}} \right) \quad \dots (15)$$

$$= C_{BigH^+} \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2^*} \right) \text{ from (7)} = C_{BigH^+} \left(\frac{k_2^* + [H^+]}{k_2^*} \right)$$

Substituting the value of $C_{BigH_2^+}$ from (14) in (15) we get,

$$x = \frac{Z (k_2^* + [H^+])}{k_2^* + 2[H^+]} \quad \dots (16)$$

Three cases are possible, depending on the relative values of x and C :

I. When x is considerably less than C , it may be assumed that C_1 present in

the mixture is negligibly small. Equations (11) and (12) are reduced to

$$C = C_3 + C_2 \quad \dots (17)$$

$$\text{and } 3C - x = 3C_3 + 2C_2 \quad \dots (18)$$

Therefore, $C_3 = x$ and $C_2 = C - x$.

Under this condition only k'_3 and K' are obtained :

$$k'_3 = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}][\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}][\text{H}^+]} = \frac{x}{C-x} \cdot \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (19)$$

and
$$K' = \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}][\text{BigH}_2^+]^3}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}][\text{H}^+]^3} = \frac{\text{Co}^{+++}}{C-x} \cdot \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]^3}{[\text{H}^+]^3} \quad \dots (20)$$

The instability constant k_3 , corresponding to the reaction,

is directly evaluated from k'_3 and k_1^* .

$$k_3 = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}][\text{BigH}^{\pm}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}]} = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}]} \cdot \frac{k_1^*[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \text{ from (6)}$$

$$= k'_3 k_1^* \quad \dots (21)$$

II. When x is greater than C but less than $2C$, C_3 present is very small, so that (11) and (12) give

$$C = C_2 + C_1, \text{ and } 3C - x = 2C_2 + C_1 \quad \dots (22)$$

therefore, $C_2 = 2C - x \quad \dots (23)$

and $C_1 = x - C \quad \dots (24)$

Under this condition only k'_1 and k'_2 are obtained.

$$k'_2 = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}][\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}][\text{H}^+]} = \frac{x-C}{2C-x} \cdot \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (25)$$

$$k'_1 = \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}][\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{'+}][\text{H}^+]} = \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}]}{x-C} \cdot \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (26)$$

The instability constant k_2 for the reaction,

is obtained from k'_2 and k_1^* .

$$k_2 = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})^{'+}][\text{BigH}^{\pm}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}]} = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})^{'+}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}]} \cdot \frac{k_1^*[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} = k'_2 \cdot k_1^* \quad \dots (27)$$

Similarly, the instability constant k_1 corresponding to

$$k_1 = \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}][\text{BigH}^{\pm}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})^{'+}]} = \frac{[\text{Co}^{+++}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2^{'+}]} \cdot \frac{k_1^*[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} = k'_1 \cdot k_1^* \quad \dots (28)$$

III. When x is greater than $2C$, both C_1 and C_2 may be regarded as very small, so that (12) gives

$$C_1 = 3C - x \quad \dots (29),$$

and the fraction $(C - C_1)/C$ of the complex is almost completely decomposed giving unstable Co^{3+} ions, which break up more or less into cobaltous ion in the following manner.

The experimental values of k'_1 , k'_2 and k'_3 may be compared with the graphical values derived according to the method of Carlson, McReynolds and Verhoek (*loc. cit.*).

$$\bar{n} = \frac{3C - x}{C} = \frac{Y_1[b] + 2Y_1Y_2[b]^2 + 3Y_1Y_2Y_3[b]^3}{1 + Y_1[b] + Y_1Y_2[b]^2 + Y_1Y_2Y_3[b]^3} \quad \dots (30)$$

where $\bar{n}$ is the ratio of biguanide still remaining in the complex to the concentration of the complex originally taken;

$$Y_1 = 1/k'_1, Y_2 = 1/k'_2, Y_3 = 1/k'_3; \text{ and } [b] = \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

In this expression Y_1 , Y_2 and Y_3 are related to formation constants as defined by Bjerrum (*loc. cit.*).

By solving (30) we may get for individual constants

$$Y_1 = \frac{1}{[b]} \times \frac{\bar{n}}{(1 - \bar{n}) + (2 - \bar{n})[b]Y_2 + (3 - \bar{n})[b]^2Y_2Y_3} \quad \dots (31)$$

$$Y_2 = \frac{1}{[b]} \times \frac{(\bar{n} - 1) + \frac{\bar{n}}{[b]}Y_1}{(2 - \bar{n}) + (3 - \bar{n})[b]Y_3} \quad \dots (32)$$

$$Y_3 = \frac{1}{[b]} \times \frac{(\bar{n} - 2) + \frac{(\bar{n} - 1)}{[b]}Y_2 + \frac{\bar{n}}{[b]^2}Y_1Y_2}{(3 - \bar{n})} \quad \dots (33)$$

When $\bar{n} = n - \frac{1}{2}$, there will be about equal number of $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{++}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{+++}$ ions in the equilibrium mixture

so that as a first approximation,

$$\frac{1}{k'_n} = Y_n = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{+++}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{++}][\text{BigH}_2^+]} = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{+++}]}{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_n^{++}][b]} = \frac{1}{[b]} \bar{n} = n - \frac{1}{2} \quad \dots (34)$$

Substituting these values in (31), (32) and (33) we get

$$Y_1 = \frac{1}{[b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{n-1}{2}}} \times \frac{1}{1 + 3Y_2[b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{n-1}{2}} + 5Y_2Y_3[b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{n-1}{2}}^2} \quad \dots (35)$$

$$Y_2 = \frac{1}{[b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{3}{2}}} \times \frac{1 + \frac{3}{Y_1 [b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{3}{2}}}}{1 + 3Y_3 [b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{3}{2}}} \quad \dots (36)$$

$$Y_3 = \frac{1}{[b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{5}{2}}} \times \left\{ 1 + Y_2 [b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{3}{2}}^3 + Y_1 Y_2 [b]_{\bar{n}=\frac{5}{2}}^5 \right\} \quad \dots (37)$$

The values of $[b]$ are obtained from the curve drawn by plotting $\bar{n}$ against $\log [b]$ or $p[b]$. Thus Y_1 , Y_2 and Y_3 may be obtained approximately from the values of $[b]$ when $\bar{n} = \frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{3}{2}$ and $\frac{5}{2}$ respectively and hence k'_1 , k'_2 and k'_3 computed.

Similar calculations are applicable to the case of cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanidinium chloride.

The mechanism represented here for the dissociation of the cobaltic biguanide complex, strictly speaking, is not a rigid one. For, in solution, complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})]^{2+}$ cannot remain as stable units, but will change readily into hexa-coordinated complexes like $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ and $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{Co}(\text{BigH})]^{2+}$ respectively (cf. Rây and Majumdar, this *Journal*, 1946, 24, 73). In fact, with increase in acidity of the solution the colour of the *tris*-biguanide complex changes from orange to violet-red and that of the *tris*-phenylbiguanide complex from red to dark red. This does not, however, affect our determination, as the concentration of water remains unchanged. In the case of copper *bis*-biguanide complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]^{2+}$ it has indeed been possible to isolate the monobiguanide complex, $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})]^{2+}$ by the addition of a limited amount of an acid (Rây and co-workers, unpublished work).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Materials

Biguanide Hydrochloride: $\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5\cdot\text{HCl}$ (in solution).—A solution of biguanide monohydrochloride (0.04M) was prepared from a solution of pure recrystallised biguanide acid sulphate by treatment with requisite quantity of KOH solution and barium chloride solution. The solution was filtered from the precipitate of barium sulphate.

Cobaltic *tris*-biguanidinium chloride was prepared and purified according to the method of Rây and Dutt (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 623). {Found: Cl, 23.07; N, 45.13. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 22.88; N, 44.85 per cent}. BigH = one biguanide molecule = $\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5$.

Phenylbiguanide Hydrochloride.—A 0.04M solution of phenylbiguanide hydrochloride was prepared from a pure and freshly recrystallised sample of the substance cf. Colln, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1911, 84, 304).

Cobaltic *tris*-phenylbiguanidinium chloride was prepared and purified by the method described by Rây and Bhattacharya (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 629). {Found: Cl, 14.41; N, 28.20. $[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 14.36; N, 28.32 per cent}. PhBigH = one phenylbiguanide molecule.

Cobalt Chloride.—A 0.02M solution of the substance was prepared from a sample of Kahlbaum's Analar quality and the strength of the solution was adjusted by an analysis of its cobalt content.

Barium chloride.—A 0.2M solution was prepared from $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Kahlbaum).

Hydrochloric Acid.—Chemically pure hydrochloric acid was distilled in an all-glass apparatus. The portion distilling over at a constant boiling temperature was collected. The strength of this solution was determined by titration with standard NaOH solution. From this solutions of weaker strength were prepared by dilution, whose strengths were further checked by titration against standard NaOH solutions.

All the solutions employed were prepared with conductivity water.

A Beckmann p_H -meter, model G, was used for p_H and E. M. F. measurements. The apparatus was previously tested by determining the redox potential of ferrous-ferric system.

Potassium Hydroxide.—A 0.337M solution was prepared from Merck's guaranteed reagent and its strength determined by titration with standard HCl.

Acid Dissociation Constants of Biguanide Hydrochloride and of Phenylbiguanide Hydrochloride

0.04M-solution of each was prepared as mentioned above. This hydrochloride solution (12.5 c.c.) was taken in each of four different 50 c.c. volumetric flasks and different amounts of 0.2M HCl solution were added to each and then the volume of the solution was made up to the mark. The p_H values of these solutions were measured by means of the Beckmann p_H -meter. The acid dissociation constant, k^*_{21} , was calculated from eq. (9). The results are given in Tables I and II.

The acid dissociation constant k^*_{12} for both the hydrochlorides was calculated by means of eq. (8) from the measurements of Das Sarma (unpublished).

Measurement of E. M. F.—The potential measurements were made in a Beckmann apparatus with saturated calomel electrode as the reference. This was directly dipped into the solution under examination, with the platinum electrode also immersed in the same solution. The apparatus was first adjusted by measuring the p_H of a buffer solution. The solution of each of the cobaltic complexes was prepared as follows: 100 c.c. of a solution containing cobaltous chloride and hydrochloric acid in different proportions were prepared. A weighed amount of the complex salt was taken and dissolved in a 50 c.c. volumetric flask by means of the above mentioned acid cobaltous chloride solution added up to the mark. This was kept at the room temperature for about three days. On the fourth day, when the system had attained equilibrium, measurements were taken. The platinum electrode was kept immersed in a portion of the solution in a test tube some hours before measurement for rapid attainment of equilibrium during the experiments. To begin with, the p_H of the acid cobaltous solution was measured using calomel and glass electrodes. Then the p_H of the complex solution was determined. Finally, the glass electrode was replaced by the platinum electrode and the potential developed was measured. The results of the experiments are arranged in Tables III—IX.

The curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against $p_{[H]}$ for solutions of the complexes are also given, where

$$\bar{n} = \frac{3C-x}{C} \text{ and } p_{[H]} = p \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{[H^+]}$$

FIG 1

TABLE I

Acid dissociation constant of biguanide, $k^{\#}_2$

Used BigH.HCl-0.01M solution = C_A ; C_A = total acid = acid added + acid as HCl in BigH.HCl. C'_A = acid corresponding to measured p_H (from the $p_H - C_A$ graph).

C_A	p_H	$C'_A \times 10^3$	$k^{\#}_2 \times 10^3$	$k^{\#}_1$
0.012M	3.62	0.2661	1.144	3.02×10^{-13} (from Das Sarma's data, loc. cit.)
0.013	3.40	0.4508	1.164	
0.014	3.23	0.6730	1.181	
0.016	2.99	1.1590	1.089	
			$k^{\#}_2$ (mean) = 1.15×10^{-3}	

TABLE II

Acid dissociation constant of phenylbiguanide (k^*_2)Used PhBigH.HCl = 0.01M solution = C_A .

C_A	p_n	$C'_A \times 10^3$	$k^*_2 \times 10^3$	k^*_1
0.014M	2.77	1.995	6.770	1.9×10^{-11}
0.016	2.55	3.311	7.660	(from Das Sarma's
0.018	2.41	4.853	8.480	(data)

 k^*_2 (mean) = 7.27×10^{-3}

TABLE III

Cobaltic tris-biguanide chloride—acid variation.

$t = 33^\circ$. Complex = 0.02M. $Co^{++} = 0.004M$. $k^*_2 = 1.15 \times 10^{-3}$. $E_0 = 1.8305$ volt at 33° . C_A = acid added. C'_A = acid corresponding to the measured p_n . x = total biguanide liberated from the complex.

C_A (corrected)	E.M.F. (in volts)	p_n	$C'_A \times 10^3$	$x \times 10^3$	$[BigH_2^+] \times 10^3$	k'_2	k'_3	k'_1	K'	$p \frac{[BigH_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$	$\frac{3C-x}{C} = \bar{n}$
0.004M	0.7029	3.37	0.483	2.770	2.0200	0.7617	...	...	65.5×10^{-18}	-0.6755	2.8615
0.008	0.7369	3.00	1.126	4.672	2.5000	0.7615	...	...	39.21×10^{-18}	-0.3978	2.7764
0.016	0.7439	2.62	2.818	7.963	2.5480	0.7028	...	...	4.99×10^{-18}	-0.0262	2.6018
0.050	0.7719	1.88	16.000	17.710	1.4200	0.8300	...	...	0.09×10^{-18}	0.9676	2.1145
0.100	0.8849	1.34	60.810	19.850	0.4870	1.4100	...	...	0.08×10^{-18}	1.9725	2.0075
0.160	0.9639	1.06	112.700	23.800	0.3101	...	8.4×10^{-4}	1.98×10^{-17}	...	2.4484	1.8100
0.200	0.9909	0.94	150.700	24.750	0.2456	...	7.2×10^{-4}	2.65×10^{-17}	...	2.6697	1.7600
0.250	1.0249	0.83	195.000	27.620	0.2129	...	8.8×10^{-4}	3.86×10^{-17}	...	2.8620	1.6190

 k'_2 (mean) = 0.765 (omitting the borderline doubtful value, 1.410) k'_3 (mean) = 8.13×10^{-4} k'_1 (mean) = 2.83×10^{-17} K' (mean) = $k'_1 \cdot k'_2 \cdot k'_3 = 0.176 \times 10^{-18}$

From curve I of the graph,

$$Y_2 = 0.11 \times 10^4; k'_2 = \frac{1}{0.11 \times 10^4} = 9.09 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$Y_3 = 0.16 \times 10; k'_3 = \frac{1}{0.16 \times 10} = 0.625$$

TABLE IV

Cobaltic tris-biguanide chloride— Co^{++} variation.

$t = 33^\circ$. Complex = 0.02M. Acid = 0.016M. $k^*_2 = 1.15 \times 10^{-3}$. $E_0 = 1.8305$ volt.

Co^{++}	R.M.F. (corr.)	p_n	$C'_A \times 10^3$	$x \times 10^3$	$[BigH_2^+] \times 10^3$	k'_2	k'_3	k'_1	K'	$p \frac{[BigH_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$	$\frac{3C-x}{C} = \bar{n}$
0.002M	0.7459	2.64	2.685	7.998	2.674	0.7776	...	...	3.50×10^{-18}	-0.0672	2.600
0.004	0.7439	2.62	2.818	7.963	2.548	0.7028	...	...	4.99×10^{-18}	-0.0262	2.602
0.008	0.7449	2.62	2.818	7.963	2.548	0.7028	...	...	5.00×10^{-18}	-0.0262	2.602
0.016	0.7499	2.60	2.972	7.727	2.427	0.6080	...	...	1.14×10^{-18}	0.0150	2.614

 k'_2 (mean) = 0.698

TABLE V

Cobaltic tris-biguanide chloride—complex variation.

$\text{Co}^{++} = 0.004M$. Acid = 0.016M. $t = 33^\circ$. $E_0 = 1.8305$ volt. $k_2^* = 1.15 \times 10^{-8}$.

Complex.	E.M.F. (corr.)	p_H .	$C_A \times 10^3$.	$x \times 10^3$.	$[\text{BigH}_2^+] \times 10^3$.	k'_3 .	k'_2 .	k'_1 .	K' .	$p \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$.	$\frac{3C-x}{C} = \bar{n}$.
0.02 M	0.7439	2.62	2.818	7.963	2.548	0.7028	...	...	4.99×10^{-10}	-0.0261	2.6012
0.015	0.7499	2.52	3.556	7.210	1.990	0.6099	...	...	2.32×10^{-10}	0.1822	2.5186
0.010	0.7559	2.39	4.864	6.250	1.377	0.5635	...	..	0.82×10^{-10}	0.47.2	2.375c
0.004	0.7479	2.11	9.333	3.587	0.463	0.5181	...	...	0.03×10^{-10}	1.2246	2.1000

k'_3 (mean) = 0.599.

TABLE VI

Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide chloride—[Co(PhBigH)₃] Cl₃, 2.5H₂O.

Acid variation.

$t = 33^\circ$. Complex = 0.02M. $\text{Co}^{++} = 0.004M$. $k_2^* = 7.27 \times 10^{-2}$. $E_0 = 1.8305$ volt.

C_A .	E.M.F. (corr.)	p_H .	$C_A \times 10^3$.	$x \times 10^3$.	$[\text{BigH}_2^+] \times 10^3$.	k'_3 .	k'_2 .	k'_1 .	K' .	$p \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$.	$\frac{3C-x}{C} = \bar{n}$.
0.004M	0.6969	2.82	1.750	1.921	1.590	0.1116	—	—	54.30×10^{-21}	-0.0213	2.9540.
0.008	0.7009	2.50	3.750	3.262	2.274	0.1402	—	—	22.20×10^{-21}	0.1433	2.8370
0.016	0.7219	2.16	8.318	5.166	2.646	0.1332	—	—	8.26×10^{-21}	0.4173	2.7420.
0.050	0.7409	1.60	31.190	10.590	2.378	0.1065	—	—	0.78×10^{-21}	1.0239	2.4700
0.100	0.7819	1.27	68.870	16.540	1.972	0.1754	—	—	0.30×10^{-21}	1.4352	2.1730
0.160	0.8059	1.05	115.900	22.970	1.728	—	33.7×10^{-4}	3.45×10^{-10}	—	1.7124	1.8515
0.200	0.8259	0.93	154.200	23.590	1.374	—	25.6×10^{-4}	3.35×10^{-10}	—	1.9319	1.8230
0.250	0.8379	0.82	199.500	25.760	1.180	—	31.5×10^{-4}	2.41×10^{-10}	—	2.1081	1.7120.

k'_3 (mean) = 0.123 (omitting the borderline value, 0.1754)

k'_2 (mean) = 30.30×10^{-4}

k'_1 (mean) = 3.07×10^{-10}

K' (mean) = $k'_1 \cdot k'_2 \cdot k'_3 = 0.114 \times 10^{-2}$

From curve II of the graph,

$Y_2 = 0.044 \times 10^4$, $k'_2 = 1/Y_2 = 22.7 \times 10^{-4}$

$Y_3 = 10.10$, $k'_3 = 1/Y_3 = 0.099$.

TABLE VII

Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide chloride—Co⁺⁺ variation.

Complex = 0.02M. $C_A = 0.016M$.

Co^{++} .	E.M.F. (corr.)	p_H .	$C_A \times 10^3$.	$x \times 10^3$.	$[\text{BigH}_2^+] \times 10^3$.	k'_3 .	k'_2 .	k'_1 .	K' .	$p \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$.	$\frac{3C-x}{C} = \bar{n}$.
0.002M	0.7179	2.17	8.128	5.311	2.752	0.1471	—	—	4.36×10^{-21}	0.3904	2.7340
0.004	0.7219	2.16	8.318	5.166	2.646	0.1332	—	—	8.26×10^{-21}	0.4173	2.7420
0.008	0.7099	2.15	8.511	5.014	2.540	0.1199	—	—	7.39×10^{-21}	0.4451	2.7490
0.016	0.7049	2.13	8.913	4.710	2.332	0.0969	—	—	2.33×10^{-21}	0.5022	2.7640

k'_3 (mean) = 0.124.

TABLE VIII

Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide chloride-complex variation.

$$\text{Co}^{++} = 0.004M. \quad C_1 = 0.016M.$$

Concn. of phenylbiguanide (corr.)	pH	$C_1 \times 10^3$	$\alpha \times 10^3$	$[\text{BigH}_2^+]$ $\times 10^3$	k'_3	k'_2	k'_1	K'	$p \frac{[\text{BigH}_2^+]}{a_{H^+}}$	$\frac{3C_1 - \alpha}{C}$	$\bar{n}$
0.020 M	0.7219	2.26	8.378	5.166	2.646	0.1332	—	—	8.26×10^{-11}	0.4173	2.7420
0.025	0.7499	2.11	9.333	4.398	2.127	0.1137	—	—	12.25×10^{-11}	0.5622	2.7113
0.010	0.7389	2.06	10.520	3.546	1.674	0.1079	—	—	4.09×10^{-11}	0.7323	2.6450
0.004	0.7249	2.02	11.480	1.941	0.815	0.0804	—	—	0.67×10^{-11}	1.0590	2.5150

$$k'_3 \text{ (mean)} = 0.1073.$$

TABLE IX

Instability constants.

$$k_3 = k'_3 \cdot k^*_{11}; \quad k_2 = k'_2 \cdot k^*_{11}; \quad k_1 = k'_1 \cdot k^*_{11}; \quad K = K' \cdot k^*_{11}{}^3 = k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3.$$

	Cobaltic tris-biguanide.	Cobaltic tris-phenylbiguanide.
Acid variation		
k_3	$0.765 \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 2.31 \times 10^{-12}$	$0.123 \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 2.34 \times 10^{-12}$
k_2	$8.13 \times 10^{-4} \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 2.46 \times 10^{-15}$	$30.3 \times 10^{-4} \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 5.76 \times 10^{-14}$
k_1	$2.83 \times 10^{-12} \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 8.55 \times 10^{-26}$	$3.07 \times 10^{-19} \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 5.8 \times 10^{-30}$
K (from direct measurement of K')	$(1805-2.20) \times 10^{-55}$	$(370-2.06) \times 10^{-64}$
$K = k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3$	4.85×10^{-56}	0.78×10^{-64}
Co ⁺⁺ variation		
k_3	$0.698 \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 2.11 \times 10^{-12}$	$0.1243 \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 2.36 \times 10^{-12}$
K (from direct measurement of K')	$(137.5-31.3) \times 10^{-56}$	$(57-16) \times 10^{-64}$
Complex variation		
k_3	$0.599 \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 1.81 \times 10^{-12}$	$0.1073 \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 2.04 \times 10^{-12}$
K (from direct measurement of K')	$(137.5-0.83) \times 10^{-55}$	$(84-4.6) \times 10^{-64}$
Graphical values (from the curves)		
k_3	$0.625 \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 1.89 \times 10^{-12}$	$0.099 \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 1.88 \times 10^{-12}$
k_2	$9.09 \times 10^{-4} \times 3.02 \times 10^{-12} = 2.75 \times 10^{-15}$	$22.5 \times 10^{-4} \times 1.9 \times 10^{-11} = 4.275 \times 10^{-14}$

DISCUSSION

From a consideration of Table I and Table II it will be observed that the acid dissociation constant of simple biguanide is smaller than that of phenylbiguanide; hence the simple biguanide, as is to be expected, behaves as a somewhat stronger base than its phenyl analogue.

A comparison of the acid dissociation constant values of the simple and phenylbiguanides with those of ammonia, aliphatic and aromatic amines, as given below, shows that as a mono-acid base, they are as strong as dialkyl and monoalkyl amines.

It has been observed that phenylbiguanide is somewhat weaker base than the simple biguanide. It will also be found from Table IX, in which the average values of instability constants for the successive partial stages, as well as for the overall stage, of the cobaltic complex with these two ligands under different conditions have been collected side by side for convenience of comparison, that phenylbiguanide, on the whole, gives rise to somewhat less stable complex than the simple biguanide. The table also shows that the overall instability constant K , determined from the direct measurement of K' , varies rather widely in each case and under any specified condition. This might evidently be attributed to the fact that the values of K' is based on the determination of cobaltic ion concentration by means of E.M.F. measurements, which required the use of E_0 of cobaltic-cobaltous system. This value was taken from Lamb and Larson's work (*loc. cit.*) after necessary temperature correction. These authors in their measurement employed strongly acid (8N) solutions, while our measurements were all made in solutions not exceeding 0.25 N in acid strength. There is likelihood that the value of E_0 for the cobaltic-cobaltous system might vary with the acid concentration of the solution leading to a variation in the overall K value. This variation might as well be caused by the fact that the cobaltic ion concentration in weakly acid solutions of the complex is negligibly small, and the slight error in its measurement is bound to give rise to widely different values. The instability of the cobaltic ion itself in solution also obviously plays an important part in causing this variation. On the other hand, the value of K can more satisfactorily be deduced from the product of the instability constants k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 for the successive partial complexes. The value of k_1 , which is also based on cobaltic ion concentration, determined from E.M.F. measurement, was found to remain fairly constant as it was measured in fairly strong acid solutions (0.16-0.25M), where an appreciable amount of cobaltic ion is likely to prevail. The values of k_2 and k_3 for both simple and phenylbiguanide complexes were also calculated from the equation derived by following the method of Carlson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) with the help of the curves obtained by plotting $(3C-x)/C$ against p ($[BigH_2^+]/a_{H^+}$). It will be found from Table IX that these agree more or less closely with the experimental values, proving thereby the validity of Carlson and co-workers' method.

The results obtained justify the assumption that the *tris*-biguanide complexes dissociate and decompose in three successive stages as already discussed. The instability constants k_3 , k_2 and k_1 for the successive *tris*-, *bis*- and *mono*-biguanide complexes, as shown in Table IX, progressively decrease, as might be expected, with the progressively decreased saturation of the co-ordinating affinity of the central cobaltic ion by the biguanide ligands. The overall instability constants ($K = 4.85 \times 10^{-55}$ for the simple biguanide complex and 7.8×10^{-65} for the phenylbiguanide complex) are quite low; that for cobaltic hexammine, as determined by Lamb and Larson (*loc. cit.*), is of the order of 10^{-34} . This is in keeping with the expectation that biguanide complexes, being of the inner metallic type, should show a greater stability than the co-ordination complexes of the usual hexammine type.

The overall instability constants for the simple and phenylbiguanide complexes may now be compared to those of inner metallic complexes of salicylaldehyde and

acetylacetonate with copper, as determined by Calvin and Wilson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2005).

Complex.	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_3 .	K .	${}^{\circ}K_{12}^{2+}$
Cu^{II} -salicylaldehyde	3.2×10^{-8}	1.6×10^{-6}	...	5.12×10^{-14}	3.2×10^{-10}
Cu^{II} -acetylacetonate	1.0×10^{-9}	8.0×10^{-9}	..	8.00×10^{-18}	2.0×10^{-10}
Co^{III} -biguanide	8.55×10^{-20}	2.46×10^{-15}	2.28×10^{-12}	4.83×10^{-45}	3.22×10^{-23}
Co^{III} -phenylbiguanide	5.8×10^{-20}	5.76×10^{-14}	2.34×10^{-11}	7.8×10^{-62}	1.9×10^{-11}

In the case of cobaltic biguanide complexes the k_1 and k_2 values are exceedingly smaller than those of copper salicylaldehyde and copper acetylacetonate, and the K_{12}^{2+} values too are somewhat smaller. Hence, the nature and valency of the central ion, as also the nature of the ligand, obviously exert a considerable influence on the stability of the complex, particularly when the ligands are of polar character, as in the present cases. The higher valency of the cobaltic ion undoubtedly increases the stability of its complexes.

Instability constants for complexes of many neutral ligands like ammonia, ethylenediamine, etc., with bivalent metals, namely Cu, Ni, Co, Zn, and Cd, have been determined by Carlson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*), as well as by Bjerrum (*loc. cit.*). These (overall K values) generally lie between 10^{-20} and 10^{-6} depending upon the nature of the metal and the character of the ligand. The cobaltic biguanide complexes therefore present instances of the most stable cationic co-ordination complexes hitherto examined.

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